

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

D6.4. Space distributed monitoring and data interpretation

Date of delivery – 23/12/2024

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This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N°101008626

DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Starting date	01.05.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	6.4
Work package number	6
Deliverable title	Space distributed monitoring and data interpretation
Lead beneficiary	University of Sheffield
Author	Alma Schellart, Yiqi Wu (USFD); Jean-Luc Bertrand Krajewski (INSA); Joerg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jose Anta (UDC)
Due date	December 31, 2024
Actual submission date	December 23, 2024
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V 0.1	Alma Schellart, University of Sheffield	14/11/2024	First draft materials included from Yiqi Wu, Carlo de Vito and Antonio Moreno Ródenas, commented on by Jose Anta and Jörg Rieckermann
V 0.2	Alma Schellart, University of Sheffield	11/12/2024	Draft updated by Alma Schellart, reviewed by Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski
V 0.3	Alma Schellart, University of Sheffield	13/12/2024	Draft updated by Alma Schellart, reviewed by Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski
V 1.0	Alma Schellart, University of Sheffield; Andrea Ciambra, Jose Anta, UDC	19/12/2024	Draft consolidation for submission

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
Co-UDlabs	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
CSO	Combined Sewer Overflow
DEFRA	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
DWF	Dry Weather Flow
DWMP	Drainage and Wastewater Management Plan
EDM	Event Duration Monitoring
EU	European Union
FFT	Flow to Full Treatment
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GVA	Gross Value Added
GWD	Ground Water Directive
IMD	Index Multiple Deprivation
LAD	Local Area District
LSOA	Lower layer Super Output Area
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PI	Performance Indicator
SOM	Self-Organising Map
SuDS	Sustainable Drainage Structures
UDS	Urban Drainage Systems
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
WP	Work Package
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WWTW	Wastewater Treatment Works

Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

The study described in this deliverable shows the potential of analysis of large spatially distributed (open) urban drainage data sets and how this may impact on regulatory policy, water utility behavior and people's behaviour.

This deliverable report compares two types of decentralized assets: Combined Sewer Overflow (CSO) structures, and Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS). This is because CSO structures have come under increased scrutiny during the process of review and recast of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) and openly available CSO spill data is becoming available in some regions. Large storage facilities (tanks), SuDS structures and real-time control are the main technical solutions to reduce CSO spills. Widespread spatial analysis of monitored SuDS performance currently does not happen. Hence this deliverable tries to take lessons learned from analysis of spatial CSO performance data and CSO related regulation and discusses what this may mean for the management of SuDS structures.

The existing Water Framework Directive (WFD) requires the combined control of point and diffuse sources, with establishment of emission control based on best available techniques or relevant emission limit values, and best environmental practices in case of diffuse pollution. The original UWWTD (1991) specified the monitoring of Waste Wastewater Treatment Works (WWTW) performance. A comparison of CSO related data collection and regulation between 10 European countries and regions has shown that this has led to a plethora of local regulations and guidelines around managing CSO performance. Assessing CSO compliance using monitored data does not happen in most countries/regions. The local regulations can be broadly divided into two types, emission based (limiting CSO spill frequency or spill pollutant load) and receiving water impact based (limiting concentration-duration-frequency of indicator pollutants in rivers). This, however, leads to a conundrum as data for simple versions of emission-based regulation such as spill frequency is relatively easy to collect but does not inform about the receiving water quality, whereas harm caused by CSO spills on the receiving water is so complex to monitor and simulate that this process is opaque and regulation becomes practically almost non-enforceable.

Analysis of the open annual CSO spill frequency and duration database from England and Wales has indicated the difficulty of trying to derive relationships between physical and socio-economical parameters and spill durations, although some correlation existed between rainfall amount, catchment steepness and duration of spills. The establishment of this open database did, however, lead to the highlighting large amounts of spills as well as the considerable investment needed to upgrade and future-proof decaying drainage systems. The recast UWWTD calls for more open performance data. Even simple but widespread (open) data can be very beneficial, for example it allows quickly noticing CSO spills occurring during dry weather. However, data should be made open with due care and in collaboration with local citizens' interest groups, social scientists and governance experts.

In several other countries, the exact number and location of all CSO structures is not known at national or regional levels, and several countries also do not have legally binding CSO emissions regulation, which makes detecting unsatisfactory spills and subsequent improving of unsatisfactory CSO structures difficult. The complexity and cost related to checking CSO compliance with receiving water impact standards means we lack oversight data concerning CSO compliance and impact on receiving waters. Inventory and performance data of SuDS structures is not widely and routinely collected, a main concern is that in several decades it will be extremely difficult to even find out where SuDS structures are and who maintains them.

1. Introduction

Urban drainage systems are deteriorating, and climate change is likely to increase pressure on these systems. There is furthermore a specific growing concern about the harm caused by CSO spills.

CSO structures were originally designed to protect against flooding, and later on to protect the WWTW against overloading. However, evidence is emerging in Europe that many CSO structures operate considerably more frequently than 'desired' (Pistocchi et al., 2019, Botturi et al, 2021), although the collected data is patchy and there are concerns about poor data quality (Dittmer et al., 2015). There is also increasing concern about micropollutants, microplastics and pathogens in CSO spills (e.g. Mutzner et al., 2022).

In European countries, there is increasing scrutiny of combined sewer overflow structures (CSOs) through the revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), as well as from the general public. Prior to the recast UWWTD, the original UWWTD (1991) specified the monitoring of WWTW performance. The current Water Framework Directive (WFD) requires the combined control of point and diffuse sources, with establishment of emission control based on best available techniques or relevant emission limit values, and best environmental practices in case of diffuse pollution. It is, however, not clear how this has been translated to monitoring and managing performance of CSOs in different areas of the EU.

Large storage facilities (tanks), SuDS structures and real-time control are the main technical solutions to reduce CSO spills. Although CSOs and SuDS assets are different in nature and operation, due to their spatially distributed nature they share some similar challenges. Widespread spatial analysis of monitored SuDS performance currently does not happen, and there are very few existing large spatially distributed datasets monitoring CSO performance.

Hence this deliverable analyses mainly existing European regulations around CSOs, as well as the openly published database of yearly event duration of CSO spills from England and Wales. Lessons learned from the analysis of spatial CSO performance data and CSO related regulation are then used to discuss what this may mean for monitoring and management of SuDS structures.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows:

- A review of CSO data collection, regulation and performance in several European countries.
- Introduction to the Open CSO data available in England and Wales.
- Spatial correlation analyses of CSO spill frequency and duration data from England and Wales
- A comparison between CSOs and SuDS, with regards to data collection, regulation and performance.
- Lessons for the future on the potential as well as the challenges of space distributed performance monitoring, open data and (potential) impacts on regulatory policy.

2. Overview of CSO data collection, regulation and performance in EU countries

This task aimed to investigate how CSO performance is regulated and how open data may be able to play a beneficial role in the performance of CSOs in EU countries. This section summarises a review and critical discussion on historic CSO design, alongside recent development of regulations, the practicalities around testing compliance, and emerging experiences of monitoring CSOs and different levels of data openness. A draft of this work has been presented at the 16th International Conference Urban Drainage (held in June 2024 in Delft, The Netherlands, Schellart et al., 2024) and a journal manuscript subsequently submitted.

2.1. Review of CSO design and performance regulation in 10 European countries/regions

A set of questions was developed to steer a review and critical discussion made by 17 researchers and practitioners in 10 European countries/regions, to investigate the level of CSO and river monitoring, local implementation of CSO regulations and its challenges. Annex 1 shows the questions list, and Table A1 summarised the findings. The countries/regions studied were England & Wales, France, Switzerland, Flanders and Brussels, Denmark, Spain, The Netherlands, Germany, Austria and Norway. Although the results from this study are not exhaustive and the countries/regions selected due to either the presence of Co-UDlabs partners or connections between Co-UDlabs partners and experts in the area, it nevertheless serves as a starting point and highlighted several conundrums related to CSO monitoring and regulation, as discussed below in this section.

This study showed how the design guidance around CSOs has evolved from relatively simple unambiguous ‘rules-of-thumb’ to guidance to limit the amount of flow going into the WWTW, and later on to more complex guidance around emissions from CSOs as well as resulting receiving water impact. As expectations and understanding of water quality impact of urban drainage have evolved with time, some of these design rules have evolved in parallel into specific regulatory requirements. However, the complexity and cost related to checking CSO compliance with receiving water impact standards means we lack oversight data concerning CSO compliance and impact on receiving waters.

An overview of the countries/regions studied in Fig. 2.1 shows that CSOs are not widely monitored, and that monitored data is not regularly used for compliance checking. Currently only in England and Wales, nearly all CSO structures are fitted with monitors that record the start and end times of CSO spills, and a database of yearly summary spill frequency and duration is openly published.

The existing Water Framework Directive (WFD) requires the combined control of point and diffuse sources, with establishment of emission control based on best available techniques or relevant emission limit values, and best environmental practices in case of diffuse pollution. The original UWWTD (1991) specified the monitoring of WWTW performance. Table A1 in Annex 1 shows that this approach has led very diverse local regulations and guidelines around managing CSO performance. The local regulations can be broadly divided into two types, emission based (limiting CSO spill frequency or spill pollutant load) and receiving water impact based (limiting concentration-duration-frequency of indicator pollutants in rivers). This, however, leads to a conundrum as data for simple versions of emission-based regulation such as spill frequency is relatively easy to collect but does not inform about the receiving water quality, whereas harm caused by CSO spills on the receiving water is so complex to monitor and simulate that this process is opaque and regulation becomes practically almost non-enforceable. For example, although England and Wales is one of the few regions that has a combined emissions and receiving water impact regulatory approach, only three out of 10 water companies occasionally carry out full receiving water impact studies. Yorkshire Water is one of these companies, and in their 2025-2030 planning period, only two

sections of river with a combined length of 28.8 km, or just over 1% of river length in Yorkshire, were required to have a receiving water impact investigation held against receiving water impact standards as laid out in FWR (2018). The estimated costs are £1,760,000 (€2,104,000), (Yorkshire Water, 2023), and this is only for collecting the data to calibrate and run the integrated water quality model to establish whether these stretches of river meet the standards. On the other hand, according to the UK Government (2024), only 14% of rivers are achieving good ecological status. This is for various possible reasons, the largest reason (40%) is given as ‘pollution from rural areas’ due to agriculture, but the second largest (35%) is pollution from wastewater due to the water industry. However, more detailed simulation in order to pinpoint specific CSOs or WWTWs, as done for the 28.8 km of river would be expensive, and the results would still be doubtful due to data and model uncertainty (e.g. Schellart et al., 2010).

Figure 2.1. Overview of CSO structure monitoring, regulation and compliance checking in 10 countries/regions studied.

In Co-UDlabs Work Package 2 (WP2), Task 2.3, a questionnaire was launched to sewer operators, asking information about their local wastewater system and whether they collect CSO related data and if so, what this data is used for. Detailed information can be found in CO-UDlabs Deliverable 2.5. Although most of the responses came from Swiss operators, the findings corroborate findings from the review made for Task 6.3, described in this deliverable report. Figures 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 from the questionnaire indicate that there is limited regular evaluation of CSO water level/spill data, and no uniform enforcement of regulation. Also, there appears an approximate 50-50 split of operators in favour or against making CSO monitoring data publicly available.

Hence more evidence would be needed to show sewer operators the potential benefits of collecting more CSO data, and also more reliable data, as well as potential of making CSO data open. However, the question also remains which type of CSO data would be best to collect, and which CSO data could best be made open and how best to do this. As widespread CSO data has been collected in England and Wales since 2020, this will be used as a case study to investigate what can be learned from a spatial analysis of this dataset, and what public reactions have been to this dataset.

Figure 2.2. Results from WP2 Task 2.3 questionnaire, regarding the existence of a legal basis for CSO monitoring, the availability of technical standards and whether existing regulation is enforced by all actors.

Figure 2.3 Results from WP2 Task 2.3 questionnaire, regarding frequency of CSO performance data collection, and what organizations the CSO performance data is shared with.

Vision 1: Real-Time Monitoring and Evaluation of Stormwater and Sewer Systems

N = 131

Vision 2: Publicly Accessible CSO Data for Enhanced Collaboration and Sustainability

N = 133

Figure 2.4. Results from WP2 Task 2.3 questionnaire, the respondent's agreement or disagreement with 2 visions for the future.

3. England and Wales open CSO EDM database

3.1. Description of the database and existing visualizations

In the UK, Department of Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), a central government ministry has required event duration monitoring of practically all storm overflows, as well as for an overview of this data to be publicly available. This requirement followed from a ‘ministerial direction’, a legal instruction from Richard Benyon the then Minister for Natural Environment and Fisheries to English and Welsh water companies. This was a very unusual action, done outside the normal consultation processes. Benyon (2013) considered increased CSO monitoring “a real opportunity for the industry to show clear leadership, to be ambitious and to quantify these ambitions and share them with their customers, the Government and more widely”. Consequently, in 2021, an openly available database of annual summaries of Event Duration Monitoring (EDM) for most storm overflows in England and Wales was made accessible (EA, 2023). In England and Wales, the term ‘storm overflow’ is used to indicate an overflow from a combined sewer system (OFWAT, 2023). This data has been visualized by NGOs such as the Rivers Trust (Rivers Trust, 2023) to reveal the spatial extent and magnitude of CSO emissions (Fig 3.1). For example, in 2021 around 372,000 spill events with a combined duration of 2,667,452 hours were recorded. The number of spills is counted using the ‘12/24’ counting method, whereby any discharges in the first 12-hour block are counted as one spill, and any discharges in the next and subsequent 24-hour blocks, are each counted as 1 spill per block (EA, 2018). Thames Water (2023) also has a near-real time map showing the occurrence of storm overflow discharges (Fig 3.2) and this is currently being rolled out by other English water companies.

Figure 3.1: Screenshot of the Rivers’ Trust ‘Is my river fit to play in’ map of storm overflows (CSO) event duration monitoring, zoomed in on the Sheffield area (Adapted from Rivers Trust, 2023).

Fig 3.2. Screenshot of Thames Water near real-time storm discharge map (Adapted from Thames Water, 2023).

The Environment Agency publishes blogs on the UK Government’s website regarding the CSO EDM data. For example, the blogpost ‘Storm Overflow spill data released today shows no room for complacency’ (EA, 2022), gives an overview of the enhancements made for the second year the full EDM database is published, and a summary of the main findings from the 2021 EDM database (DEFRA, 2022; Table 3.1). Headlines are reported in the blog, such as “The data shows that the average number of monitored spills per overflow has reduced from 33 in 2020 to 29 in 2021, with significant variance between water and sewerage companies (min/max average 20/42 spills). While the trend appears to be going down, this is most likely a result of drier weather in parts of the country last year than in 2020”.

Table 3.1. Summary overview of the headlines of the 2021 EDM data, from DEFRA (2022).

2021 EDM Headlines	Anglian Water	Welsh Water (in England)	Northumbrian Water	Severn Trent Water	South West Water	Southern Water	Thames Water	United Utilities	Wessex Water	Yorkshire Water	Water Company Totals / Average
Total no. storm overflows listed in the annual return in 2021	1552	124	1567	2658	1391	978	465	2192	1297	2246	14,470
Total no. storm overflows with EDM commissioned	842	123	1542	2437	1102	963	465	2006	1049	2178	12,707
% overflows listed with EDM commissioned	54.3	99.2	98.4	91.7	79.2	98.5	100	91.5	80.9	97.0	89
Total no. storm overflows with spill data	834	121	1440	2412	1093	943	461	1954	1048	2087	12,393
Average no. spills per storm overflow with spill data in 2021	25.6	29.5	25.3	24.7	38.9	20.2	31.9	41.8	22.4	33.6	29.4
Average duration (hrs) per monitored spill event in 2021	9.1	4.8	6.0	7.7	8.3	8.4	11.1	6.6	6.4	5.8	7.4

3.2. Analysis of England CSO EDM database since its publication

The open CSO EDM database has generated considerable public concern. As a result of this, in England, a government-led Storm Overflow Taskforce has been established to make recommendations on how to prevent harm from storm overflows in England. This Taskforce consists of representatives from DEFRA, the water industry, regulators (Environment Agency and OFWAT), NGOs (Rivers Trust and Water UK) and the Consumer Council for Water respectively. The Stormwater Overflow Taskforce has commissioned Stantec (a consultant) to carry out the Storm Overflows Evidence Project (SOEP, Gill et al., 2021). The SOEP report investigated potential impacts from a subset of 9,248 CSOs as these were in urban areas for which a hydraulic sewer model was available. The SOEP report did not use the recorded CSO EDM data, as models were necessary to simulate overflow volumes for the subsequent calculation of river impact, network storage and impermeable area runoff. Note that the number of simulated spills represented in the SOEP report was 26% lower (251,808) compared to the number of measured spills (342,346), as the modelled structures are not necessarily the same ones as the monitored ones, some are only monitored and not modelled and vice versa. The key findings of the SOEP report describe policies and scenarios to limit the annual average number of spills to 40, 20, 10, 5 and 0, differentiating between a universally applied limit, or limits only for 'sensitive' catchments, and using three scenarios, storage (grey infrastructure) only, storage with a low uptake of SuDS (Sustainable Drainage Structures), and a high uptake of SuDS. A modelling approach was used to estimate costs, customer's bill impacts, and carbon associated with these scenarios. For example, a policy focused on achieving 40 spills per year in general, and 10 spills per year in sensitive catchments would cost between £18 (€ 36) billion and £110 (€ 132) billion, which would impact annual household bills between £30 (€ 36) and £208 (€ 238) per year. These estimated increases in water bills attracted press coverage and discussions on the management of Water Utilities in England, receiving water quality and the costs of reducing harm from CSO spills. These debates are still ongoing: Schellart et al. (2024 – submitted manuscript) discuss this further.

4. Spatial Correlation Analyses of CSO EDM data England and Wales

This chapter reviews published literature on spatial correlation analysis of the CSO EDM data from England and Wales, as well as subsequent analysis carried out as part of the Co-UDlabs project. Annex 2.1 describes briefly how the data is made open and how much is known about the data quality.

4.1. Spatial correlation CSO EDM data England scale

As described in the Storm Overflows Evidence Project (SOEP, Gill et al., 2021), generally more CSO spills were seen in the North-East of England and Wales, but local differences were observed. A frequency distribution of the spill frequency and duration data from 2021, for all water utilities corroborates this general trend (Annex 2.3, Fig. A2.6). Initial investigations of the 2021 and 2022 EDM database also showed the majority of spills occurring near the WWTW, either the storm tanks near the WWTW or at the WWTW inlet (Fig. A2.5). Giakoumis and Voulvoulis (2023) hypothesized that where WWTW are particularly under capacity, a larger duration of CSO spills would be seen at the treatment works. Using CSO structures' location database, information and population information to estimate the capacity of WWTWs in multiples of average DWF revealed a chronic under-capacity of WWTWs and showed that wastewater systems with insufficient capacity (defined as 3*DWF for large and 6*DWF for small systems) had on average higher CSO spill durations compared to systems with sufficient capacity (in the years 2020 & 2021 studied).

This work was extended by Co-UDlabs to spatially visualise spill durations (from 2021) of CSO structures together with WWTW capacity (as calculated by Giakoumis and Voulvoulis, 2023) in boundaries of <1 DWF, 1-2 DWF, 2-3 DWF, 3-6 DWF, and >6 DWF. A visual inspection for all English Water utilities did not show clear spatial patterns, and considerable outliers where a WWTW with sufficient capacity still showed long CSO durations at and near the WWTW and vice versa, see Annex 2.2 for some examples.

As no consistent relations between CSO spill duration and WWTW capacity were found, more detailed spatial correlation analysis was carried out. For this analysis, the 2022 CSO EDM data was selected as this was the latest data made available in 2023 when the study was started, and the 2020 and 2021 datasets have less CSO structures included. The yearly summary by the Met Office data shows 2022 to have below average rainfall: 90% of the 1991-2020 average (Met Office, 2023).

4.2. Spatial Correlation CSO EDM data England & Wales at Local Authority District scale

Deltares supervised a student placement project for a master's student from TUDelft, The Netherlands, who explored spatial patterns between CSO spill durations on the one hand, and geographical, environmental and economic factors on the other hand, at Local Authority District Scale (LAD, UK Government, 2023). An overview of the results was presented at the 16th International Conference of Urban Drainage in Delft in 2024 (De Vito et al., 2024). Following the CSO EDM data from the year 2022, out of 330 LADs in England and Wales examined, 326 had CSOs reported in the EDM database.

The average CSO spill durations within the LADs were calculated by aggregating total durations and dividing by the number of CSOs. ArcGIS Pro version 3.1.3 was used to conduct both global and local spatial analyses based on this aggregated data.

4.2.1. Results and discussion LAD level spatial analysis

The analysis of the 2022 EDM data at LAD level reveals a right-skewness towards long CSO spill durations as illustrated in Figure 4.1. Certain LADs show a high average spill duration.

Figure 4.1. Histogram and box-plot of the average CSO spill durations in England and Wales in 2022 (Vito et al., 2024).

A spatial autocorrelation analysis based on the Global Moran's I statistic indicates these LAD averaged CSO spill durations are statistically significantly clustered at both local and broader scales, notably within a 90 km distance band. Using the identified 90 km distance band, the LISA (Local Indicator of Spatial Association) analysis (Annex 3, Fig. A3.2 & A3.3) revealed that LADs with longer CSO spill durations are mostly found in the western and northern regions, while those with shorter durations are in the eastern and southern regions. The analysis also highlighted the presence of statistically significant spatial outliers, which may suggest LADs with notably different drainage system performance compared to neighbouring areas with similar climatic conditions and catchment characteristics. This indicates that local unidentified factors may have a significant impact on drainage network performance.

Further analysis showed that local patterns in CSO spill durations are correlated with rainfall, catchment slope, percentage built-up area and weakly correlated with GDP (Figures 4.2 & 4.3). Refer to appendix A3 and Figure A3.1 for a description of the methodology to calculate average LAD slope. LADs with higher annual rainfall and steeper slopes tend to experience longer average annual CSO spill durations, and areas with lower GDP showed longer CSO spill durations. There is also weak-negative correlation (not shown) between percentage of built-up area and duration of monitored LAD-averaged CSO spill event durations, which showed stronger negative correlation for LADs with steeper slopes (not shown). However, it is difficult to disentangle between different contributing factors, as steeper areas historically tend to be less popular places for settlements, larger settlements tend to be found in flatter areas and GDP is also weak-positive correlated with total percentage of built-up area.

Figure 4.2. Relationship between LAD-averaged CSO spill durations and Average Total Annual Rainfall (left) and Average catchment Slope (right) (Vito et al., n.d.).

Figure 4.3 Relationship between LAD-averaged CSO spill durations and GDP categories (Vito et al, n.d.).

Recent sewer system assets design takes account of local weather conditions, using locally derived design rainfall. However, in the UK, many CSOs still in operation are legacies of infrastructure established prior to the 1980s. During that period, CSO structures were designed to limit the pass-forward flow to the Wastewater Treatment Works (WWTW), typically set to six times the dry weather flow (Butler et al., 2018). This may explain the observed patterns in the LISA cluster map, with longer CSO spill durations in regions with higher annual rainfall volumes, such as the western and northern areas in the UK. Moreover, these regions also include steeper terrain, which leads to faster runoff and higher net discharge per unit area. However, these correlations are relatively weak, suggesting the presence of additional local factors that influence CSO spill durations.

4.3. Spatial correlation CSO EDM data at wastewater catchment and Lower layer Super Output Area (LSOA) scales

To investigate more localised patterns as well as correlation between multiple variables, further spatial correlation analysis is based on a smaller spatial level, using the Self Organising Maps (SOM) technique (Refer to Annex 3.3 for explanation of the SOM technique).

The analysis is conducted at the scale of wastewater catchments and Lower layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs). LSOAs consist of areas which have a residence population between 1,000 and 3,000 persons (ONS, 2021; the site includes openly available shapefiles). Wastewater catchment shapefiles were obtained from existing freedom of information requests, an overview map is shown in Figure 4.4.

Table 4.1 Variables investigated in the SOM analysis

Variable Name	Description
mean_totalDuration	Average of the annual spill duration (hours) of all the CSOs in the wastewater catchment
mean_CountedSpill	Average of the annual number of spills of all the CSOs in the wastewater catchment
sum_totalDuration	Total of the annual spill duration (hours) of all the CSOs in the wastewater catchment
sum_CountedSpill	Total of the annual number of spills of all the CSOs in the wastewater catchment
slope	Average slope (percentage) of the wastewater catchment
Area	Area (m ²) of the wastewater catchment
builtup_Area	Built-up area (m ²) inside the wastewater catchment
builtup_prt	Percentage of the built-up area inside the wastewater catchment
Population2002	Population in 2002
Population2022	Population in 2022
PopulationChange0222	Percentage of population change from 2002 to 2022
PopulationDensity2002	Population density in 2002
PopulationDensity2022	Population density in 2022
Deprivation	Overall Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) Score
DeprivationClass	Whether wastewater catchment intersect with at least one LSOA that is in the top 20% deprived areas, 1 for yes, 0 for no
GVA_10Yr	Average Gross Value Added (over the period 2004-2023)
mean_GVA_10Yr	Average Gross Value Added per capita (over the period 2004-2023)
FFT_DWF	Flow to Full Treatment /Dry Weather Flow (only for areas where this information could be found)
WWTW	Whether FFT/DWF data could be found (1 for yes, 0 for no)
Rain	Millimetres of rain received in the catchment area in one year (2022) based on weather radar data.
RainVol	Total amount of rain (litres) received in the catchment area

Variable Name	Description
RainCount_6hr	Number of rainfall events counted in the year, defined as >0mm of rain, with a 6-hour dry weather period separating events
RainCount_filtered_6hr	Number of rainfall events filtered based on thresholds of > 15 mm in 24 hours and > 10mm in 6 hours; with a 6-hour dry weather period for event separation) with a 6-hour dry weather period separating events
CompanyID	A water company ID number assigned from Northwest to Southeast (Northumbrian Water 1, United Utilities 2, Yorkshire Water 3, Welsh Water 4, Severn Trent Water 5, Anglian Water 6, Thames Water 7, Wessex Water 8, Southern Water 9)

Figure 4.4: Location of the wastewater catchments under analysis, (except South West)¹

¹ Freedom of information requests data: Anglian Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa#incoming-2001959, Northumbrian Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_4#outgoing-1239170, Severn Trent:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_6#outgoing-1268506, Southern Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_7#outgoing-1239168, Thames Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_9#incoming-1949301, United Utilities Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_10#incoming-1948526, Wessex Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_11#outgoing-1244771, Yorkshire Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_2#outgoing-1244772, Yorkshire Water:

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/wastewater_catchment_area_geospa_12#outgoing-1243463.

Wastewater catchment information for South-West Water was not found in the public domain. The data were sourced from the Environment Agency’s “Consented Discharges to Controlled Water with Conditions” database (EA, 2023; work carried out by de Vito et al., n.d.). Geographical coordinates were adjusted through a verification process referencing Environment Agency information and satellite images, in order to link each WWTW to a single catchment.

A range of demographic, geographic and weather-related variables were investigated, as shown in Table 4.1. Annex 3.3 explains in detail how these variables were derived, which datasets were used, and how LSOA areas were linked to sewer catchments.

4.4. Results and discussion SOM analysis on wastewater catchment and LSOA scale

Six SOM analyses were produced: a set for **average** spill count and duration for **all** sewer catchments, split out between sewer catchments where a WWTW could be associated with the catchment (around one third of sewer catchments), and catchments for which it was not possible to work out where the associated WWTW was. This set of three was then repeated for **total** spill count and duration.

Figure 4.5 shows an example output from the SOM analysis for **total** spill count & duration and **all** parameters for all sewer catchments, the other SOM results are not shown here, they are still being investigated in more detail and a journal paper manuscript is in preparation. Annex 3.3 explains in detail how to read a SOM, but in short the colours correspond to the value of a variable (red for high value, blue for low value), and the pattern indicates whether variables are correlated or not. For example, in Figure 4.5, a very similar pattern can be seen for the variables ‘sum_totalDuration’ (2nd panel from left in top row) and ‘sumCounted Spill’ (3rd panel from left in top row). This means that e.g. sewer catchments with a high total duration of CSO spills show a high spill count, as expected. The initial observations made from the full set of six SOM analyses can be summarized as:

- The total duration and the number of spills in wastewater catchments are highly correlated, which means that usually with high number of spills, the total duration of the spills are also high.
- The total duration and number of spills in wastewater catchments are highly correlated, which means that in catchments with a high number of spills, the total duration of the spills is usually also high.
- The total spill is slightly positively correlated with percentage built-up area. All the high spill frequency areas fall into areas with low population density, although not all low-population density areas have high-frequency spilling CSOs.
- The total spill is also correlated with total rain volume. This means that with higher rainfall volume, it is expected to have a higher duration and count of spills in a wastewater catchment area. This is also partially due to the fact that rainfall volume is calculated as the rainfall intensity times the catchment area, since area is correlated with the total spill, rainfall volume is also influenced by a similar pattern.
- The average spill duration is slightly correlated with slope. This may be due to the fact that slope will affect the ‘peakiness’ of the runoff response, and the rate of infiltration hence leading to higher and steeper runoff peaks.
- The average duration and number of spills is correlated with rain depth over the sewer catchment and number of filtered rainfall events. The correlation between average spills and number of ‘filtered’ rainfall events (number of events > 15 mm depth in 24 hours and > 10mm depth in 6 hours; with a 6-hour dry weather period for event separation) is stronger for the sewer catchments that could not be

associated with a WWTW. The two most Northerly water utilities also fall into an area of high number of rainy periods (Rain_count6hr).

- For both average and total spills, the catchments with a high number of spills are clustered within a larger region of high built-up percentage (hence not all regions with a high built-up percentage show high total and average number of spills).
- For both average and total spills, the catchments with a high number of spills are clustered within a larger region of high number of rainfall events.
- For both average and total spills, the catchments with a high number of spills are clustered within a larger region where wastewater catchment intersect with at least one LSOA that is in the top 20% deprived areas.

Figure 4.5. SOM of total spill count & duration and all parameters for all sewer catchments (both those that could be linked to a WWTW and those that could not be linked to a WWTW)

Overall, the findings from the SOM analysis at the smaller sewer catchment and LSOA scales confirm the general findings from the analysis at the larger LAD scales. But again, the correlations are relatively weak. This may indicate that there are still many unidentified localized variables that may influence the frequency and duration of CSO spills, as well as the influence of possible errors in the various databases used. The ‘summary data’ sheets provided by the Environment Agency with the EDM data (EA, 2023) indicates a variety of reasons given by the water utilities

for the CSO structures which spilled > 60 times per year. Only a small percentage is ascribed to 'exceptional weather', a slightly larger percentage is due to 'operational' reasons (incl asset maintenance), and the majority is due to 'hydraulic capacity reasons'. Hydraulic capacity reasons could be very localized and dependent on the local lay-out of the pipe network.

5. Comparison of CSOs and SuDS: spatial data for performance and regulation

Both CSOs and SuDS are decentralised urban infrastructures aiming to control stormwater at the city scale. They are different in nature and operation but share some similar challenges and issues. SuDS are furthermore utilised as one of several solutions aimed at reducing CSO spills (e.g. Cavadini *et al.*, 2024).

This chapter will compare CSO data collection for managing performance and compliance with regulation and discuss how lessons learned from this could be applicable to SuDS.

As mentioned in Chapter 2, the aim of CSOs and their design guidelines were revised when WWTW were introduced to combined sewer systems, to limit inflows to WWTP during rainfall, as well as to avoid flooding urban areas. From this point of view, CSOs are designed to discharge as frequently as necessary to protect downstream WWTW. However, from the receiving water body's point of view, CSOs are a problem and a source of negative impacts on water bodies ecology. Hence additional design guidelines were developed for CSOs to limit their impact, such as inclusion of screens and storage/settling basins.

A development of the last two decades is to try to reduce the amount of urban flooding and/or the volume and pollutant loads of CSO spills, by introducing SuDS to reduce the amount of stormwater entering combined sewer systems. SuDS can also have many other potential benefits, such as urban runoff treatment, amenity, urban biodiversity and urban heat island reduction. However, SuDS are also seen as more difficult to manage (compared to a CSO tank or RTC system) due to e.g. their decentralised nature, varied ownership and varying institutions/individuals responsible for their maintenance. Furthermore, compared to CSOs, there is an even wider range of design guidelines (e.g. Woods-Ballard *et al.*, 2015, Andrés-Doménech *et al.*, 2021) and potential performance indicators for SuDS, e.g. runoff volume reduction, runoff treatment and/or amenity (Ferreira Santos *et al.*, 2019).

Hence currently CSO spill data, SuDS performance data and receiving surface/ground water quality data is collected for different purposes, and to evaluate compliance against different regulations, e.g. UWWTD, WFD and GWD (Ground Water Directive). This causes challenges when updating regulations/design rules when older infrastructure is held against newer rules, while they were not originally designed to satisfy these new rules (Schellart *et al.*, 2024, submitted). Globally, there is crucial lack of consistency of design, operation and performance assessment rules of artificially separated components of global water systems.

5.1. The number of CSO structures and SuDS structures

Table A 1.1. shows the number of CSO structures known (inventoried according to various criteria) or estimated in the 10 countries/areas studied in this deliverable. Other reports put this at 650,000 CSO structures in Europe (EurEau,2020), with smaller numbers reported in Milieu *et al.* (2016) and Table A1.1. It is clear there are several areas where the number of CSO structures is known to be unknown, and there are country-specific sub-categories of definitions of overflow structures. For example, in England and Wales an overflow structure at a pumping station is not considered to be a storm overflow (the English definition of a CSO), but an 'emergency overflow'.

The number of SuDS structures is rapidly growing, and this number is expected to become considerably larger number than the number of CSOs.

For example, in England, Severn Trent received COVID recovery funding from the government and are currently installing 20,000 SuDS structures in Mansfield (population 110,500; ONS 2022), with the aim of reducing flooding (Severn Trent, 2024). By comparison, according to the CSO EDM data set, there are around 20 CSO structures in

Mansfield, thus approximately 1000 times more SuDS structures than CSO structures. Although it must be noted that the SuDS schemes in Mansfield were introduced with the specific aim of reducing flood risk. It is difficult to estimate exactly how many SuDS structures there may be installed in Europe in the coming decades. However, it makes intuitive sense that the number of SuDS structures may far exceed the current number of CSO structures. Nearly every street, building or block could end up with some type of SuDS, e.g. permeable paving, tree pits, green roofs or water butts. In a very rough thought experiment: if 1 in 10 households ends up with a SuDS structure associated with it, and there are 200 million households in the EU (Eurostat, 2024) this would equate to 20 million SuDS structures in Europe. As seen from chapter 2 as well as CO-UDlabs Deliverable 2.5, it is already very challenging to monitor all CSO structures, hence monitoring all existing and planned SuDS structures would be even more challenging. In such a context, scientifically based procedures will be necessary to identify representative SuDS to be monitored in a given area to estimate their global combined performance at catchment scale, as it will be simply impossible to monitor all SuDS.

5.2. Monitoring and metrology – CSOs vs SuDS

CSOs are diverse and most frequently complex hydraulic structures, where simple standard hydraulic equations for discharge calculations given in textbooks cannot be applied. CSOs have been designed with rules and criteria which evolved significantly during the last 150 years (Chapter 2, more detail in Schellart et al., *subm.*). To accurately calculate CSO discharge and/or volume, a case-by-case hydrodynamic analysis is usually required, with 3D modelling as a tool to calculate discharge (Fach et al., 2009; Momplot, 2014). There are ‘simpler’ binary yes/no methods of monitoring whether a spill occurs, although the reporting of this varies (e.g., 2 spills in a 24 hour period counted as 1 spill or as 2 spills).

SuDS are even more diverse in nature and design, frequently with more than one inflow and outflow, and with a larger range of potential aims (e.g. reducing flood risk and/or reducing CSO spills, treating runoff, increasing amenity, reducing heat island effect). Therefore, a case-by-case analysis would be required to implement an adapt a performance monitoring system. In addition, all SUDs involve hydrological processes such as infiltration into the soil and/or evapotranspiration, which are very difficult to routinely monitor by practitioners. Hence evaluating the hydrological performance of SuDS by means of a water balance monitoring is a significant difficulty (see examples in Bertrand-Krajewski et al., 2021).

Understanding the hydrodynamic performance of CSOs and hydrologic/hydrodynamic performance of SuDS does not inform on receiving surface and/or ground water quality, or risk to human health. For both CSOs and SuDS, monitoring discharged pollutant loads is difficult, and would involve extensive sampling strategies with lab analyses, or continuous monitoring with sensors.

One of the most basic data, the location of a CSO structure, is usually located in a sewer system which tends to have a small number of owners (Water Utility, water company and/or municipality) is known reasonably well, at least locally. Several European countries/areas have some form of permitting in most areas, which means there are asset location databases, but this is not the case in all areas (Chapter 2, Milieu et al., 2016). However, for SuDS structures this information is much more difficult to obtain, partly but not only due to a much wider variety of public and private ownership. Data is not systematically collected and reported: only local and partial inventories exist, not necessarily aiming to assess performance, but most frequently to provide examples, cases studies, etc. to create incentives for the installation of more SuDS. For example, in the region of Lyon, France, the GRAIE has

created a regional observatory of exemplary SuDSHYPERLINK projects.² In the USA a database exists (see <https://bmpdatabase.org/>), but only a part reports about performances. There is clearly an urgent need for improvement at the international level.

5.3. Performance Indicators

Performance indicators (PIs) must reflect the objectives given to CSO infrastructures and SuDS and be linked consistently with policy and decision-making criteria. PIs used during design of infrastructure are also not necessarily suitable for use as PIs in regulatory standards (Mohan, 2024).

PIs must be clear, non-ambiguous, based on measurable quantities. Possible misuses, biases and problems must be anticipated. This is, however, easier said than done.

Section 2 and Annex 1 illustrate the difficulty of selecting the right level of PI for CSOs. PIs should be not so simplistic that it does not provide the information needed, but also not so complicated that it becomes very difficult to monitor, and either model estimations (containing opaque assumptions) are used, and/or people will find ways to avoid having to check against the PI.

A review by Ferreira Santos et al. (2019) on stormwater systems PIs concluded that most of the research works were of limited scope, focusing on single storm water systems or some specific aspects of their performance, and also gave an inappropriate definition and selection of PI, compromising their further application. The identified gaps emphasise the need for a new methodology to provide a reference framework in the field. Such methodology should be objective, standardised and well-adapted to different contexts, driven by objectives and criteria and based on PI and targets.

5.4. Data quality, representativeness, uncertainty and reliability

Metrology and monitoring of CSOs and SuDS most frequently suffer from insufficient attention, resources, skills and incentives, leading to poor quality data when data exist (e.g. low reliability, significant bias and not quantified uncertainties, insufficient data validation, lack of periodic checking, missing quality assurance/quality control). In the Co-UDlabs project WP6, the UDMT – Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox has been developed as a free software tool aiming to contribute to the necessary training and change of practice (Bertrand-Krajewski and Lepot, 2024).

For both CSOs and SuDS, uncertainties in monitoring data as well as in models are too rarely assessed and reported. Furthermore, if uncertainties would be reported, there would then need to be agreements and definitions on risk, which are currently not there. For example, would a water utility or a regulator accept 90% or 75% confidence in meeting the PIs? (Sriwastava et al., 2021). It also implies that regulation and compliance criteria must evolve to also account for unavoidable uncertainties in data.

Representativeness is a key issue: monitoring all CSOs is costly, but measuring only a sub-set of CSOs requires additional hypotheses and modelling for selecting it and interpreting the global impact of all CSOs (including the non-monitored ones) on the receiving water bodies.

In the case of **SuDS**, the representativeness challenges are similar, yet cost of widespread monitoring SuDS could become at least one order of magnitude higher, due to the potential numbers of SuDS structures installed in the next decades (Section 5.1).

² See: <https://asso.graie.org/portail/animationregionale/techniques-alternatives/>.

Scientific literature already introduced, years ago, the concept of decentralised SuDS which are monitored locally and whose functioning and operation is coordinated at a centralised wider catchment or sub-catchment scale, aiming to achieve a global optimized action (e.g. Han and Mun, 2011). However, it seems that this concept, despite its relevance having been shown theoretically several times by means of modelling (e.g. Miao et al., 2019), has been rarely implemented in practice at large spatial scale by operators up to now (e.g. Li et al., 2024), and that, to our best knowledge, no large monitoring data set was publicly available for analysis in this WP.

6. Discussion, conclusion and lessons learned

6.1. Performance Indicators for CSO management, a conundrum

Monitoring CSO performance indicators (PIs) throughout the EU is not widespread, data is rarely publicly available, and assessing CSO compliance with data does not happen regularly. There are advantages as well as disadvantages linked to all the diverse PIs currently used for CSO management. Simple emission-based PIs (such as spill frequency) are relatively easy and cheap to evaluate but do not inform on the impact on receiving water quality. More complex PIs (such as emissions of pollutant load from CSO spills, or the impact of CSO spills on receiving water) are far more difficult and expensive to determine, involving the need for long term datasets that are naturally variable, models with considerable levels of uncertainty, and a high potential for opaque decision making.

Near-real time simple CSO spill data, such as binary spill data (a CSO has occurred yes/no), as is currently being rolled out both for the majority of CSO structures in England and Wales and for around one-third of CSO structures in Flanders, can inform on whether or not a CSO is spilling during dry weather (Dircks et al., 2022) and how often during wet weather. That a CSO structure should not spill during dry weather is a generally agreed upon unambiguous PI reflecting non-compliant sewer infrastructure. Too frequent spills during wet weather, despite the difficulty to assess this quantity (see below), may also provide evidence that the sewer infrastructure does not function satisfactorily.

All the other more elaborated PIs involve some form of ambiguity, increasing with the PI complexity. The number of CSO events (spill frequency) per year needs an agreement on how to count CSO events, (e.g. daily or per event, and what time should separate 2 events). Due to spatial and temporal variability of rainfall, it is ambiguous to determine what is considered 'too many' spills, and what is considered an 'acceptable spill' due to 'excessive' rainfall.

Discharged CSO spill volumes and/or discharged pollutant loads (as per the recast UWWTD: storm water overflow should represent no more than 2 % of the annual collected urban wastewater load calculated in dry weather conditions. This also phrased as an 'indicative objective'). This PI involves ambiguity, in e.g. how to measure or model the annual overflow load, and establishing this number will likely always involve models, with considerable associated uncertainty (also shown experimentally by e.g. Co-UDlabs Transnational Access projects in the RTC facility in USFD).

Only a very limited number of countries have receiving water impact related PIs, which try to link CSO spills and receiving water quality impacts. Currently only 3 out of 10 English Water Companies and Denmark regularly test their CSOs against some form of receiving water impact PI. The models are known to contain considerable uncertainty, and source apportionment (i.e. stating which specific CSO structures are causing the problem) has so much ambiguity associated with, that making a legal case is very difficult.

Unfortunately, detailed academic screening studies have not found simple correlations between readily observable variables (such as rainfall volume, intensity, storage volume and land use) and receiving water impacts (e.g. Engelhard et al., 2008). This is not surprising, as it depends also on i) many other variables (e.g. succession of dry and wet periods, initial conditions, sewer maintenance practice, or some random contributions on the catchments) and ii) variable state and characteristics of the receiving water at the moment of the CSO spill (e.g. season, antecedent conditions). It is also to be expected as urban drainage systems are originally designed to protect an urban area, and not to protect the receiving water course. Dittmer et al. (2015) analysed data from the state of

Baden-Württemberg and did not find correlations; however, they found various problems with the quality of the database. Hence an advantage of monitoring data is that they help to identify problems in planning data.

Hence planned openly available water management plans (as described in both the recast UWWTD and the UKs Environment Act) are expected to aid the management of CSOs through enabling open discussion around what is acceptable and acknowledging ambiguities.

6.2. Large spatial datasets

The analysis of the CSO EDM database, covering nearly all CSO structures in England and Wales, showed correlation between yearly amount of rainfall and catchment steepness at both local area district scale and sewer catchment scale, although the correlations were weak. The frequency distribution of the spill frequency showed a right-skew to high frequency (>60 spills per year) for all areas. Although from an engineering perspective, it is hard to decide exactly at what number of spills a CSO structure 'operates as designed', this number is high and indicates a considerable number of sewer systems that are failing. The reasons for these spills given is mostly 'lack of hydraulic capacity', and most spills occur at the downstream end of the sewer catchments, near the WWTW.

For SuDS, no comparable large scale performance dataset was found. It is anticipated that the amount of SuDS structures will far outnumber the amount of CSO structures, and it is concerning that there is no widespread collection of databases with even the minimum information, the location and type of SuDS structure.

Producing large data sets for numerous decentralised and spatially distributed infrastructures requires anticipating several aspects: financing, availability of skilled staff, data storage, archiving, formatting, access and the FAIR principles. Co-UDlabs Deliverable 2.2 describes in detail the challenges and opportunities in harmonizing Urban Drainage data across the EU.

6.3. Public access to urban drainage data

In England and Wales, CSO EDM data was made public, and this came about after lobbying by citizens in a very unusual way: through a ministerial direction. In Switzerland, only around 50% of the Swiss practitioners agreed on 'making data open being a good thing' (Fig. 2.4). The benefit of open urban drainage data should be demonstrated more widely and clearly to practitioners, with examples.

Open data can play an important role in more transparent governance and decision making, and it is advocated in the recast UWWTD. Public access to more urban drainage data is desirable, but the data must be made open with due care, or it can lead to much anger and finger pointing which is drawing attention away from collaborative discussions on solutions, as explained in Schellart et al. (submitted manuscript). In England and Wales, the openly accessible CSO performance data has drawn attention to decaying urban drainage networks, which are otherwise invisible to the public. It created open discussion on how to reduce the amount of CSO spills, the costs of improvements and why improvements cannot be made imminently. Openly available explanatory documents are published, for example by the Institution of Civil Engineers (ICE, 2023).

Open data can also encourage the public to help (by e.g. installing SuDS on private properties), as advocated on the City to Ocean website following the openly available Brussels CSO data (City to Ocean, 2024)

However, very clear illustration and explanation is needed about how to interpret / understand the data, a consensus between stakeholders is necessary and collaboration with local citizens groups, social scientists and communication experts is crucial.

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Annex 1. Review of CSO regulation, compliance assessment and open data

In order to review local CSO related regulations, compliance checking, design guidance and available data, the following questions were posed to experts from 10 regions/countries in Europe and the answers discussed among the experts:

- What is the number of CSO structures in your country/region? Who owns/operates & controls these CSO structures?
- What principle drove the historic design of CSO structures?
- What is the principle driving design of “new” CSO structures/ upgrades to existing CSO structures?
- How are existing CSO structures regulated? Is this spill frequency, spill volume, receiving water impacts, or a combination of these?
- How many CSO structures are monitored, using what parameters?
- Is CSO spill data used in regulation compliance assessment, and if so, what type of data is used for this?
- Does assessing compliance with data happen regularly or only in certain cases?
- What happens if illegal CSO spills occur? Who is responsible for follow-up investigation & preventing recurrence?
- Is CSO data made public? If so, what type of data is made public, and through what mechanism is this made public? Can the data be easily understood?
- Is river quality data collected regularly? If so, what data. Is this data country-wide and made open to the public?
- Are there any type of local citizen action groups concerned with river quality? Are they utilising and/or scrutinising data? Is there media impact from open data?

An overview of the findings is summarised in Table A1. A more detailed discussion of the findings, and overview of historic developments of CSO design and CSO related regulations is described in (Schellart et al., 2024 submitted manuscript)

Table A1: Comparison of CSO monitoring, regulation and compliance assessment in several European countries (Schellart et al., 2024 submitted manuscript)

Questions	England/ Wales	France	Switzerland	Belgium	Denmark	Spain	Netherlands	Germany	Austria	Norway
Number of CSO structures.	14,530	9468	est. 5,000 (no official statistics.	Flanders: est. 8,000 Brussels: est. 100	4,257	7995 for 80% of territories	est. >15,000	25,909 simple with tanks	Estimated 10,300	3928
Ratio of nr. inhabitants/nr. CSO structures	4108	7200	1748 (estimated)	990 (Flanders & Brussels combined)	1394	n/a	1187	1824 (all types CSOs combined)	884	1418
How are existing CSO structures regulated?	Emission based (Pass-forward flow). Occasionally Moving to Emission + river impact based	Emission based. (Municipality decides): spill frequency, or spill volume, or pollutant load	Receiving water-impact based. Some cantons different (e.g. spill duration in Basel)	Flanders: Emission based (Spill frequency)	Emission based. Nr. of CSO events, yearly volume, max discharge (l/s/ha).	Emission based (spill volume) and receiving water impact based in some cases	Emission & sensitivity of the receiving water based	Emissions based Permits based on simulation results for COD. No additional regulation is applied.	Emission-based. Legally binding regulation planned since 1996, but adoption failed.	Emission based. (Rules vary based on p.e. thresholds. spill duration and pollutant load in overflow for larger systems)
How many CSOs are monitored, using what attributes?	13,323 CSO structures (2022), start and end time of spill monitored	Not publicly known at national level. Data could be obtained at municipal level or from Water Agencies	Unknown at national level. Data could be obtained at utilities. Reporting not obligatory	Brussels: 50% of CSO structures (Frequency & duration, simulation of the volume via level & velocity data). Flanders: 30% CSOs monitored (VMM)	Most are simulated. 0.6% has monitoring of spill quality, 7% monitoring of hydraulic parameters.	Upcoming: all sewer systems >50000 p.e. will be monitored (spill duration, volume, some cases pollution).	In some areas monitoring is obligatory, the monitoring network is growing.	Not widely done (only for certain types of CSOs, i.e. with tanks); monitoring of CSOs with tanks compulsory in 2 of the 16 federal states	Unknown at national level	Unknown at national level.

Questions	England/ Wales	France	Switzerland	Belgium	Denmark	Spain	Netherlands	Germany	Austria	Norway
Is monitored or simulated CSO spill data used in regulation compliance assessment?	Yes, monitored spill duration data	Depends, monitored or simulated (largest CSO structures must be monitored)	Not yet. Permits based on simulated emissions. Some cantons ask for CSO attributes.	Brussels: A reporting of monitored CSO spills happened at yearly basis by 'Brussels Environment'	Each municipality has to report the (mostly simulated) yearly discharges	Upcoming: river basin authorities will be informed and simulated CSO data	No, just to get an indication of the evolution of spills	No. Permits are based on simulated emissions	No. Only very limited data available. Where available, mostly measured voluntarily and not made public	Depends, monitored or simulated. Limited data on permits to be reported annually. Nr & duration, m ³ & kg tot-P are asked 'if available'.
Does assessing compliance with data happen regularly or only in certain cases?	Spill frequency regularly assessed. Receiving water impact only rarely	Municipalities must report CSO compliance. Evaluated yearly from data collected in previous 5 yrs.	No, currently no legal requirements for CSO monitoring and reporting	Brussels: Follow-up on a yearly basis	Compliance checked by the Environmental Agency, but controls are not sufficient	Just in few cases and depending on the river basin authority	No	Not regularly. Only if data are far out of the expected, water authority might interfere.	No, currently no legal requirement for CSO monitoring and reporting existing.	In theory, yes. Control visits to check if compliant with permits, but frequency of visits is not regulated.
What happens if illegal spills occur? Who is responsible for follow-up & preventing recurrence?	Fines for breaches of EA spill permits. Water utilities negotiate with EA & OFWAT on investment in 'solutions'.	Municipalities are responsible. If illegal spills are detected, the source is investigated (but difficult to find)	Legal action only for spills by private entities. If a municipality contaminates environment: nothing happens	Brussels: In case of illegal spill detection, 'Brussels Environment' tries to track its source, but often very difficult.	Theoretically the responsible entity can receive a fine. In practice this only very seldomly occurs	Fines for illegal spills. CSO compliance has been applied in just few cases till now, as regulation since 08/23	Theoretically the responsible organisation/person can receive a fine. In practice this only very seldomly occurs	No standard procedure. No regulations on spills. Difficult to categorize a spill during wet-weather as illegal.	Nothing. There are currently no legal requirements for CSO monitoring and reporting existing	Private persons or companies get fines. If permit violated by a municipality, procedure is followed that may end in a fine, but mostly in a discussion on solutions.

Questions	England/ Wales	France	Switzerland	Belgium	Denmark	Spain	Netherlands	Germany	Austria	Norway
Is CSO data made public, if so, what data, through what mechanism.	Event frequency and duration by EA, through big .csv files. Visualisations by NGOs	CSO data are not public	Yearly performance report of utility (authors only know of 1 utility which does it regularly)	Brussels: data collected via FLOWBRU is Open Data	Yes, public homepage. NGO & journalists provide visualizations	No. Only some Aggregated data, not easy to understand	No. Basically all data are open, but they are not easily accessible: only via a formal request	No. Citizens have a legal right to information, only via formal request	No	No. All permits, control protocols and data are public, but mainly focused on WWTWs. CSO data not public.
Is river quality data collected, regularly, if so, what data; is it country-wide and made open to public?	Yes, 160 stations for continous monitoring plus infrequent grab samples & invertebrate surveys. Data openly accessible through EA	Yes. These data are made publicly available, e.g. on websites of Water Agencies.	Yes, but not always continuously. Grab samples in selected rivers. Data public and country-wide.	Brussels: Continuous measurement of the main 2 CSO-receiving water bodies.	Yes. River data available online, the number of monitored rivers is small, so several data are outdated	Yes. River data at selected gauging stations used for river basin management plans. Data is openly available.	Yes, monitoring, water quality and warnings are issued (e.g. risk to swimmers).	Yes. Monitoring according to requirements of the EU WFD. Not specifically related to CSO events.	Yes, monitoring according to requirements of the EU WFD. Not specifically related to CSO events.	Yes. How regular depends on the waterbody.
Are citizen groups or NGOs concerned with river quality? How are they utilizing data? Media impacts?	Yes, NGOs and river custodian groups using data. Costs of sewer upgrades in policies of all major parties & discussed in media.	Yes, NGOs with concern about river quality. Not frequently concerned with CSOs.	Yes, and also national action groups. Not actively scrutinizing, but occasional media coverage	Brussels: Yes. 'Canal It Up' uses the CSO data to raise awareness on the impacts of CSO spills.	CSO data in newspapers every year. Big focus on CSO from farmers association	Not yet. Some action groups debated separate v.-combined sewer and SuDS implementation	Yes, e.g. the NGO 'Natuur & Milieu' incidently reports results of monitoring campaigns.	River quality is only in the media related to spectacular events causing large scale fish kill.	Currently no, since no CSO data is currently publicly available	Yes. Mainly by fishery groups. No big public debate/media impact visible. Growing public concern water quality Oslofjorden.

Annex 2. General analysis EDM CSO data England and Wales.

A2.1. England and Wales CSO EDM data

Data on CSO spills in England and Wales is collected by the Water Companies since 2020, and an overview of the data is sent every year to the Environment Agency. The overview contains yearly summaries of the spill frequency and duration for each CSO structure in the database, and the percentage of the reporting period that the data collection was operational. If the reporting was operational for less than 90% of the time, a reason is given (such as 'comms failure', and when this was resolved). It also provides a reason for high spill frequencies (as provided by the Water Utilities) and whether any action is taken/planned. This data is provided as an Excel Workbook with a Tab for each water company. Also provided for each CSO structure is the site name, the EA Permit reference and details on the permit type, the asset type (e.g. whether a storm discharge at a pumping station, at a storm tank at the WWTW or on the sewer network, the water body ID and name where it discharges to and whether this is a designated shellfish water or bathing water, and which date the EDM was commissioned). Each year around March/April, the database from the year before is published. The databases have currently been published for 2020, 2021, 2022 & 2023 on the government data platform, which also contains a Dataset Documentation sheet with information about the data and some yearly summary statistics and a long-term trends statistics overview document which gets updated each year (Environment Agency, 2024a). The Grid Reference coordinates of the CSO structures are provided in the Permits database (EA, 2024b).

A2.2. Comparing WWTW capacity and CSO duration at the WWTW.

In Giakoumis and Voulvoulis (2023), the CSO EDM database was linked to data on the WWTW and population data. It was hypothesized that where WWTW are particularly under capacity, a larger duration of CSO spills would be seen at the treatment works. In CO-UDlabs, as part of an undergraduate student placement project, maps were created for each English Water Utility visualising the WWTW capacity (in boundaries of <1 DWF, 1-2 DWF, 2-3 DWF, 3-6 DWF, >6 DWF as calculated by Giakoumis and Voulvoulis, 2023), together with the reported durations of CSO spills occurring. However, the maps show that not all locations show a higher duration of spills in sewer catchments where there is low WWTW capacity, and vice versa.

For example, Figure A2.1 and A2.2 show the spill hours from the 2021 EDM data (brown circles), overlaid with the WWTW capacity (coloured triangles) as estimated by Giakoumis and Voulvoulis (2023), for the city of York and the surrounding area, Figure A2.3 & A2.4 show this for the area around the city of Leicester. 'Large' WWTWs have been defined here as treating >286m³/day and small WWTW as treating <286m³/day. York shows a large WWTW with more capacity (3-6 DWF), yet Leicester, served by several large WWTW with lower capacity (between 1-3 DWF), showed shorter spill durations compared to York. This investigation also showed one example of a WWTW near Leicester (Wanlip), which according to Giakoumis and Voulvoulis (2023) has sufficient capacity, yet according to a study done for Leicester City Council it is near capacity (JBA Consulting, 2023). This illustrates the uncertainty involved trying to link different sources of spatial information (as was acknowledged by Giakoumis and Voulvoulis), but the study also illustrates the interest of the City Council in the Water Company's Drainage and Wastewater Management Plan (DWMP).

Initial investigation on the 2021 & 2022 database furthermore showed most of the CSO spills do occur at the downstream end of the sewer catchments, e.g. at the storm tanks near the WWTW or at the inlet of the WWTW.

Figure A 2.1 York and surrounding area, Large Treatment Works capacity overlaid with EDM duration data from 2021. (Archie Browne, Undergraduate student placement project at Sheffield University)

Figure A 2.2 York and surrounding area, small Treatment Works capacity overlaid with EDM duration data from 2021. (Archie Browne, Undergraduate student placement project at Sheffield University)

Figure A 2.3 Leicester and surrounding area, large Treatment Works capacity overlaid with EDM duration data from 2021. (Archie Browne, Undergraduate student placement project at Sheffield University)

Figure A 2.4 Leicester and surrounding area, small Treatment Works capacity overlaid with EDM duration data from 2021. (Archie Browne, Undergraduate student placement project at Sheffield University)

Figure A2.5 Average annual CSO spill hours for 3 water utilities subdivided by asset type. (Archie Browne, Undergraduate student placement project at Sheffield University)

A2.3. Frequency distributions of spill frequency and duration per water utility for 2021

Figure 2.6 shows spill frequency distribution of spill durations per water utility for 2021. Note that the y-axes are not on the same scale, due to the differences in size of the water companies. However, the heavy-tailed ‘right skewed’ pattern is the same across all water companies.

A 2.6 Spill frequency distribution of spill durations per water utility for 2021, Alex Smith USFD student placement project.

Annex 3. Local Authority District Scale and sewer catchment scale analysis of England and Wales CSO EDM data

A3.1. Methodology of LAD analysis CSO EDM data

To define suitable neighbourhoods for LADs, the Fixed Distance Band method was used, which assigns equal spatial weights to features within a specified distance from each other. This distance was measured using the Euclidean method, and row standardization was applied to create proportional spatial weights, a recommended approach to mitigate bias resulting from the imposed aggregation scheme (ESRI, 2023a).

The Spatial Autocorrelation tool was deployed to evaluate spatial structure. This tool computes the Global Moran's I statistic and a single z-score value, indicating the extent of clustering or dispersion of the entire study area (ESRI, 2023b). To determine the fixed distance band that best reflected localized patterns of spill durations, the tool was applied across various fixed distance band values. In order to identify local dependencies, LISA (Local Indicator of Spatial Association) analysis using the Cluster and Outlier Analysis tool was conducted. This tool operates similarly to Hotspot Analysis, as it can identify spatial clusters of short (cold spots) and long (hot spots) CSO spill durations. However, it also evaluates each individual LAD influence on the global statistics, enabling the identification of statistically significant spatial outliers. Using Local Moran's I statistics, the tool classifies LADs into categories like high-high, low-low, high-low outliers, and low-high outliers (ESRI, 2023c).

Having identified spatial patterns within the 2022 EDM dataset, several potential factors influencing the observed CSO spill patterns were explored. The impact of rainfall was assessed by utilizing the HadUK-Gridded Climate Observations dataset (MetOffice, 2023) for 2022, and calculating the average annual rainfall amounts for each LAD. The influence of topography was studied by computing the average slope for each LAD. This calculation was based on a 90-meter resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) provided by Pope (2017), see Figure A3.1.

Fig. A3.1. methodology to calculate average slope for each LAD (de Vito, n.d.)

A3.2. Results of LAD analysis CSO EDM data

The spatial autocorrelation analysis based on the Global Moran's I statistic indicates that the LAD averaged CSO spill durations are statistically significant clustered at both local and broader scales. Notably, within a 90 km distance band, the analysis identified the first peak in the z-score, approximately 21, and a corresponding p-value

close to zero. This distance was selected as the most appropriate for the local analysis, aligning with recommended best practices outlined by ESRI (2023d) for fixed distance bands. Using the identified 90 km distance band, the LISA analysis (Figure A3.3 and A3.3) revealed that LADs with longer CSO spill durations are mostly found in the western and northern regions, while those with shorter durations are in the eastern and southern regions. Moreover, the LISA cluster and significance maps highlights the presence of statistically significant spatial outliers. These outliers, shown in darker colours, may suggest LADs with notably different drainage system performance compared to neighbouring areas with similar climatic conditions and catchment characteristics. This indicates that local unidentified factors may have a significant impact on drainage network performance.

Figure A3.2 LISA cluster map based on the average of the total duration of monitored CSO spill events in 2022 (de Vito, n.d.)

Figure A3.3 LISA significance map based on the average of the total duration of monitored spill events in 2022.

A3.3. Introduction to Self-Organising Maps

SOM is a type of unsupervised ANN which is used for spatial data clustering. Unlike a supervised ANN, there is no hidden layer of neurons in the learning process of SOM. There are only two layers: an ‘input layer’ and a so-called ‘competition layer’. By using a ‘competitive learning’ approach, SOM produces a nonlinear mapping from an m -dimensional space of attributes to a two-dimensional lattice of cells or neurons (Kind and Brunner, 2013). As shown in Figure A3.4, a training set of n vectors of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , is mapped into a lattice of K neurons. A neuron contains a vector of weights $(w_{i1}, w_{i2}, \dots, w_{im})$ associated with all the input attributes and with the same dimension of m . The colour of the map encodes the organization of groups of samples/observations with similar properties.

Figure A3.4: A schematic representation of a Self-Organizing Map (source: Kind and Brunner, 2013).

The SOM training process consists of a few steps over many iterations:

1. Initialise the weights of neurons.
2. A vector from the input data (a sample in the data) is presented to the lattice and the weight vectors of the neurons in the output layer are compared with the input vector.
3. The neuron with the most similar weights to the input vector is selected as its 'Best Matching Unit' (BMU). This is done by calculating the Euclidean distance between weight vector and input vectors.
4. The weights of the neighbouring neurons of the BMU are updated to make them more like the input vector but with a smaller degree, according to their distance to the BMU.
5. The neighbourhood is defined by a circle with a certain radius which decreases gradually over the training process.
6. Steps 2-5 are repeated until the change of the weight vectors falls below a certain threshold, i.e. the clusters are formed.

A3.3.1. Example – Railway Track Flooding

The usefulness of SOM has been demonstrated through a study on the railway drainage related failures (Wu, 2022) where SOM was employed to examine the relative strength of the plausible linkages between various input parameters and observed railway track flooding. The identification of strong relationships has helped pinpoint the influencing parameters that are the causes of failures.

Railway track flooding is defined as the incidents recorded when train is under speed restriction or stopped due to excess of water present above the railway track. Several parameters have been investigated using SOMs to test for linkage to Track Flooding failures, such as drainage, structural and service asset condition, precipitation and local geology. The result shows that two parameters are identified to be important: 1. Average drainage assets condition within a 100 m radius of the failure location at the time of the failure, 2. Total precipitation volume in (mm) 5 days before the failure date at the failure location.

Figure A3.5: Relationships between Failure, total precipitation in the last 5 days, and average service condition score

The SOMs graph is presented in Figure A3.5. On the maps, each cell (neuron, represented by a colored hexagon) represents a group of observations; the spatial location of a cell in a topographic map corresponds to a particular domain or feature drawn from the input space. The colour of the cells represents the value of the variables where red is high, and blue is low. Each cell in the same position on different maps corresponds to the same group of observations/samples. Note that it does not matter where on the maps the clusters form (as this depends on how the weight vectors are initialised and how a vector from the input data is selected and presented to the lattice), but the important point is that the neurons (and patterns) at the same position on different maps correspond to the same group of samples in the data.

As shown in the Figure A3.5, two clusters are formed due to the Failure map (lattice C), which is marked by the dashed lines. The number in the Failure map indicates whether a failure occurred, where 1 means failure happened and 2 means there is no failure. As expected, the failure is linked to a higher precipitation level as there are lots more red cells in the upper cluster in the 5-day total precipitation map (lattice A). The linkage between asset service condition is less obvious, however, in the service condition map (lattice B), there is slightly less cells with a low condition score (better condition) in the cluster corresponding to failure (Wu, 2022).

In addition to the maps of parameters, the SOM analysis provides an additional lattice called unified distance matrix, or 'U-matrix' (see Figure A3.5, left). A U-matrix represents the 'distance' between neurons in the process of determination of the BMU of the samples. Therefore, cells with larger U-matrix values (i.e. red cells on the U-matrix lattice) are far from other cells with respect to the input space, while the ones with blue colour are closer to each other. This suggests that blue areas on the U-matrix correspond to the clusters and red lines correspond to where the clusters are separated, i.e. cluster separators.

A3.4. Explanation of the variables used in the SOM analysis

A3.4.1 Slope

A catchment slope raster that used a 90 m resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM), as provided by Pope (2017) was used in this study. The average slope for each wastewater treatment catchment was calculated using the “Zonal Statistics” tool from ArcGIS Pro.

A3.4.2 Built-up Area

The Built-up Areas data from Ordnance Survey (<https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/products/os-open-built-up-areas>) was used. Overlap of build-up areas and wastewater catchments was determined using the ‘Intersect’ tool in ArcGIS Pro, and the total amount of build-up area calculated for each catchment. An example is shown in the Figure A3.6, where the green polygons are the build-up area and the polygons with red outline are the wastewater catchments.

Figure A3.6: An example of overlapping wastewater catchments (red outlined polygons) and build up area (green polygons).

A3.4.3 Population

Population estimates by lower super output area (LSOA) as published by Office for National Statistics (Lower Layer Super Output Areas (December 2021) Boundaries EW BFC (V10) | Open Geography Portal, n.d.) were used in this study. The population of each sewer catchment was estimated by linking the LSOAs to the wastewater catchments using the ‘Intersect’ tool in ArcGIS Pro. The population in each LSOA was distributed based on the area of the wastewater catchment overlapping with the LSOA: if n wastewater catchments (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n) overlapped with an LSOA that has a population Q , and the overlapping areas are (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n), then the population in the overlapped area of catchment w_i is equal to

$$Q \times \frac{A_i}{\sum_{k=1}^n A_k}$$

Figure A3.7 illustrates an example of overlapping wastewater catchments (red outline) and LSOAs (the purple polygons covering the whole figure). As shown in Figure A 3.7, some of the smaller wastewater catchments are contained within an LSOA covering a large area, whereas the large wastewater catchments are consistent of many small LSOA areas. Not the LSOA are areas with a resident population between 1,000 and 3,000 residents, so rural LSOAs cover a large area, and urban LSOAs cover much smaller areas.

Figure A3.7: Example of overlapping wastewater catchments (red outlined polygons) and LSOAs (purple polygons).

A3.4.4 Deprivation and Deprivation Class

The Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) is a measure of relative deprivation across each of the constituent nations of the United Kingdom. Multiple components of deprivation are weighted with different strengths and compiled into a single score of deprivation. Deprivation factors include income, employment, education, health, crime, barriers to housing and services, and the living environment. IMD is used in this study to investigate whether there is a relationship between socio-economic factors and CSO spills. The latest IMD data released in 2019 is provided by Office for National Statistics on the LSOA level (Mapping Income Deprivation at a Local Authority Level - Office for National Statistics, n.d.). The IMD for each wastewater catchment is estimated using the same method as estimating the population data. The IMD is a score ranging from 1-100, and as the wide range maybe harder to interpret, a 'DeprivationClass' variable was also included, which is a binary split (1 for yes, 0 for no) as to whether wastewater catchment intersects with at least one LSOA in the top 20% deprived areas.

A3.4.5 Gross Value Added (GVA_10yr) and Gross Value Added per capita (Mean GVA 10yr)

Gross value added (GVA) is the measure of the increase in the value of the economy due to the production of goods and services, recorded in millions of pounds). It is a measure of the contribution to Gross Domestic Product made by an individual producer, industry or sector. The GVA estimates are produced from 1998 to 2021 at LSOA level and provided by Office for National Statistics (UK Small Area Gross Value Added (GVA) Estimates - Office for National Statistics, n.d.). Since the most recent GVA estimate is from 2021, this study uses the average GVA from 2012 to

2021 as an estimate for 2022. GVA is used in this study to investigate whether there is a relationship between economic development and CSO spills. The GVA is estimated for each sewer catchment using the same method as estimating the population data, based on the proportions of each LSOA overlapping the sewer catchment area. Gross Value Added per capita (Mean GVA 10yr) gives the average GVA per capita.

A3.4.6 Flow to Full Treatment /Dry Weather Flow (FFT_DWF) and WWTW

The ratio of Flow to Full Treatment (FFT) and Dry Weather Flow (DWF) is used to represent the hydraulic capacity of a Wastewater Treatment Works (WWTW). The FFT represents the maximum flow that the WWTW can effectively treat at any given time, and the dry weather flow (DWF) is the average daily flow to a treatment facility during periods without rainfall. The FFT/DWF ratio, therefore, serves as an indicator of the system's capacity to handle increased hydraulic loads during wet weather conditions (De Vito et al., n.d.). However, not all the sewer catchments had both DWF and FFT available, so this analysis could not be carried out for all sewer catchment. Therefore a binary variable 'WWTW' was added, indicating whether a WWTW could be linked to a catchment this way, with 1 for yes and 0 for no.

A3.4.7 Rainfall ('Rain') and Rainfall volume (RainVol)

The rainfall data used in this study is the Met Office Rain Radar Data from the NIMROD System, rainfall depth in mm, recorded on 1 km grids with a 5-minute frequency. Nimrod is a fully automated system for weather analysis and nowcasting based around a network of C-band rainfall radars. Data for 2022 are downloaded from the CEDA (Center for Environmental Data Analysis) Archive site (Met Office, 2003). For each wastewater catchment, the amount of the catchment area that falls into each 1km grid is calculated using the 'Intersect' tool in ArcGIS Pro, and the total rainfall depth for one year calculated. The proportion of rainfall contributed by each grid is presented by the proportion of the intersected area over the total catchment area. Total amount of rainfall is then calculated by adding rainfall from all contributing grids. Rainfall volume is the volume of rainfall, calculated by multiplying the rainfall depth by the catchment area, and expressed in litres.

A3.4.8 Rainfall events (Rain_Count_6hrs) and Rainfall events over thresholds (Rain_Count_Filtered)

The number of rainfall events are analysed using the rainfall time series for each catchment derived from the radar data. A single rainfall event is defined as a period when the average precipitation over the catchment is above 0, separated by a minimum of 6 hours of 0 rainfall. The rainfall events are also filtered based on the three thresholds described in Table A3.1. These threshold values are somewhat arbitrarily selected, to be one-year return period event for that duration in all parts of the country. The 'Rain-Count_Filtered' counts all rainfall events above this threshold which occurred in the sewer catchment in the year studied. This is to provide some form of comparison between the number of 'large' but not 'extreme' rainfall events, and the number of CSO spills occurring. The thresholds used in this study is shown in the Table A3.1.

Table A3.1: Rainfall event thresholds used in SOM analysis compared to 1-year return period rainfall events according to the 'Wallingford Procedure' (Hydraulics research limited, 1981)

Duration	Threshold used in SOM (mm)	1-year return period rainfall depth in NorthWest UK (mm)	1-year return period rainfall depth in SouthEast UK (mm)
24 hours	15	20	28
6 hours	10	13	20

A3.5. References

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